

WEBGA YO'NALTIRILGAN DASTURLASH TILLARI

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1. **HTML: Hyper Text Markup Language - veb-sahifalarni yaratish uchun ishlatiladigan belgilash tili.**
2. **CSS: Cascading Style Sheets - HTML-dokumentlarning stilini belgilash uchun ishlatiladigan dasturiy tillar jami.**
3. **JavaScript: brauzerda ishlaydigan, dasturni boshqaruvchi tili.**
4. **PHP: server tomonidan ishga tushiriladigan, dinamik veb-saytlarni yaratish uchun ishlatiladigan tilda.**
5. **Ruby: dinamik veb-saytlarni va xavfsizlikni ta'minlash uchun ishlatiladi.**

HTML Hyper Text Markup Language degan ma'noni anglatadi. Bu veb-sahifalarni yaratish va loyihalash uchun ishlatiladigan kompyuter tili. HTML veb-sahifadagi matn, rasmlar, havolalar va shakllar kabi ba'zi elementlar qanday ko'rsatilishi kerakligini ko'rsatish uchun teglardan foydalanadi. HTML fayllari odatda .html yoki .htm kengaytmasi bilan saqlanadi va ularni Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox yoki Microsoft Edge kabi veb-brauzerlarda ko'rish mumkin. HTML CSS (Cascading Style Sheets) va JavaScript bilan bir qatorda veb-ishlab chiqishning muhim tarkibiy qismidir.

CSS (Cascading Style Sheets) veb-saytlar va internet ilovalarini dizayn qilish uchun ishlatiladigan bir tilda shakllantirilgan dasturdir. CSS, saytning chizig'larini aniqlash va uni stilini belgilashda foydalaniladi. Bu yordam bilan, HTML-da matnni, rasmni, video va boshqa elementlarni ko'rsatish mumkin.

CSS, HTML-da qo'shma sifatida foydalaniladi. Bu saytda istalgan elementga stil berish imkoniyatiga ega bo'lish uchun HTML faylining tarkibi ichida CSS kodlari ham mavjud. Bunday qilib, matn rangi, fon rangi, yechim ko'rinishi kabi turli tuzilmalar o'zgartirilishi mumkin.

CSS dasturlash tili juda kuchli va shunchaki o'rganishi ham oson. Uning yordamida siz saytingizni har qanday xil dizaynga o'tkazishingiz mumkin. CSS kodlarini HTML-faylingizga joylashtirishda esa siz saytingizni noma'lum darajada muhim darajaga ko'tarib chiqarasiz.

CSS-ni HTML bilan birgalikda ishlatib, veb-saytlarning shaklni va ko'rinishini boshqacha yaratishingiz mumkin. Ushbu usul bilan siz o'zingizning so'nggi tasavvuringizga moslik etadigan eng samarali veb-saytlarni tuzishingiz mumkin.

Javascript interaktiv va dinamik veb-saytlarni yaratish uchun foydalaniladigan dasturlash tilidir. Bu mijoz tomonidagi skript tili bo'lib, u veb-saytni joylashtiradigan serverda emas, balki foydalanuvchi brauzerida ishlaydi. Javascript HTML va CSS-ni manipulyatsiya qilish, animatsiyalarni yaratish, shakllarni tekshirish va API va ma'lumotlar bazalari bilan ishlash uchun ishlatilishi mumkin. Bu bugungi kunda eng mashhur dasturlash tillaridan biri bo'lib, barcha asosiy veb-brauzerlar tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanadi.

React - bu foydalanuvchi interfeyslarini yaratish uchun JavaScript kutubxonasi. U Facebook tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan va ko'plab mashhur veb-saytlar va ilovalar, jumladan Instagram, Airbnb va Netflix tomonidan qo'llaniladi. React ishlab chiquvchilarga murakkab foydalanuvchi interfeyslarini yaratish uchun birlashtirilishi mumkin bo'lgan qayta foydalanish mumkin bo'lgan komponentlarni yaratishga imkon beradi. U ishlashni optimallashtirish va o'zgartirishlar kiritilganda faqat foydalanuvchi interfeysining kerakli qismlarini yangilash uchun virtual DOM (Hujjat ob'ekt modeli) dan foydalanadi. React, shuningdek, server tomonida ko'rsatish imkonini beradi, bu esa SEO-do'st bo'lgan tez yuklanadigan veb-sahifalarni yaratishni osonlashtiradi.

PHP qisqartmasi Hypertext Preprocessor degan ma'noni anglatadi. Bu dinamik va interaktiv veb-saytlarni ishlab chiqish uchun ishlatiladigan server tomonidagi skript tilidir. PHP kodi serverda veb-sahifa mijozning brauzeriga yuborilishidan oldin bajariladi, bu esa ma'lumotlar bazalariga kirish va foydalanuvchi ma'lumotlarini qayta ishlash kabi yanada rivojlangan funksiyalarga imkon beradi. PHP HTML kodiga kiritilishi yoki mustaqil til sifatida ishlatilishi mumkin. Bu ochiq manba bo'lib, uning rivojlanishi va takomillashuviga doimo hissa qo'shadigan katta ishlab chiquvchilar hamjamiyatiga ega. PHP-dan foydalanadigan ba'zi mashhur veb-saytlar orasida Facebook, Vikipediya va WordPress mavjud.

Ruby — 1990-yillarning o'rtalarida Yaponiyada Yukixiro Matsumoto tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan yuqori darajadagi, dinamik dasturlash tili. U oddiy va ifodali sintaksis bilan o'qish va yozish oson bo'lishi uchun yaratilgan.

Ruby - bu ob'ektga yo'naltirilgan til, ya'ni Rubydagi hamma narsa ob'ektdir. Funktsional, imperativ va protsessual dasturlash kabi bir nechta dasturlash paradigmalarni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi. U ishlab chiquvchilarning unumdorligi va moslashuvchanligiga katta e'tibor qaratadi, bu uni veb-ishlab chiqish, skript yaratish va avtomatlashtirish uchun mashhur tanlovga aylantiradi.

Ruby-ning ba'zi muhim xususiyatlari quyidagilardan iborat:

- Dinamik yozish: o'zgaruvchilarni ma'lum bir ma'lumot turi bilan e'lon qilish shart emas.
- Chiqindilarni yig'ish: ob'ektlar ishlatilmaganda avtomatik ravishda xotirani bo'shatadi.
- Bloklar: boshqa usullarga argument sifatida uzatilishi mumkin bo'lgan anonim funktsiyalar yoki kod bloklarini aniqlash uchun kuchli konstruktsiya.
- Metadasturlash: kodni yozadigan yoki ish vaqtida mavjud kodning harakatini o'zgartiradigan kod yozish qobiliyati.
- Ochiq darslar: ish vaqtida mavjud sinflarning usullarini qo'shish yoki o'zgartirish imkoniyati.

Ruby-da veb-ishlab chiqish uchun Ruby on Rails, engil veb-ilovalarni yaratish uchun Sinatra va infratuzilmani avtomatlashtirish uchun Chef kabi ko'plab mashhur ramkalar mavjud. Shuningdek, u o'rganish va rivojlantirish uchun onlayn mavjud bo'lgan boy resurslarga ega kuchli hamjamiyatga ega.

Xulosa:

Ushbu tezisda Web dasturlashda kerak bo'ladigan dasturlash tillarini tahlil qildik. Biz Web dasturlashga kirishimizda qaysi dasturlash tillarini o'rganishimiz va ularni qay maqsadda ishlatishiz tushuntirib o'tilgan

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